

DEVELOPING TECHNICAL SKILLS OF TECHNOLOGY AND LIVELIHOOD EDUCATION SECONDARY TEACHERS IN THE PROVINCE OF BATANGAS

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ABSTRACT

This study assessed the level of competency of teachers in technology and livelihood education relative to their instructional performance in the Province of Batangas with the purpose of developing a competency management program for TLE teachers. It likewise aimed to describe the personal and professional characteristics of TLE teachers; determine the level of competencies along the four areas of TLE; measure the level of competencies of TLE teachers; show whether there is significant relationship in the level of competencies of TLE teachers and their profile variables; identify the competency needs of TLE teachers; and develop a competency management program for TLE teachers. The study used the descriptive method of research as it aimed to assess the level of competencies of TLE teachers in the Province of Batangas. The respondents were mostly aged from 36-45, female, with less than 10 years of teaching experience, Baccalaureate degree, had attended six to eight seminars and had very minimal exposure to research endeavors. The TLE teachers had great manifestations in terms of competencies relative to Home Economics and Industrial Arts while moderate manifestations were recorded for Agri-Fishery Arts and Information and Communication Technology. They were very competent in terms of knowledge of content within and across curriculum teaching areas, strategies and methods, classroom management, integration of ICT, and assessment and evaluation. Analysis yielded the indication that there is a need to strengthen teachers' skills in applying range of teaching strategies through LAC sessions. A need in terms of attending to different TLE-focused seminars and trainings in developing competencies in teaching TLE was also seen as well as improving TLE teachers' ICT skills to address learning goals for daily lesson integration. There was also a need in terms of engaging faculty members in collegial coaching to brainstorm on best teaching methodologies, supporting TLE teachers by transforming weak areas into strength through technical assistance and equipping laboratory rooms with complete tools, equipment and paraphernalia for each course offered. There was a need to further develop the competency of teachers, therefore, a competency management program for TLE teachers was designed for implementation as determined by the results of the assessment.

Keywords: Teaching and Learning, Technical Skills, Competency Needs, TLE Teachers, Descriptive Method, Philippines